

ADDITIONS TO THE PTERIDOPHYTE FLORA FROM JALPAIGURI DISTRICT OF EASTERN HIMALAYAN FOOT HILLS REGION, WEST BENGAL

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ABSTRACT

As part of the studies on fern and fern-allies diversity from Jalpaiguri district of the Eastern Himalayan foot hill region of northern part of West Bengal, India several fern species were explored. In the process, 26 species of pteridophytes among all identified species were identified as new addition to the concerned district pteridophyte flora. A taxonomic account of 26 different fern and fern-allies here are belongs to 20 genera of 12 different family. Detailed description, a synonym/basionym for each taxon, photo-plates for each species, local distribution in WB, conservation status and specimens examined is provided for the further references.

Key Words : Conservation, Eastern Himalaya, Jalpaiguri, Pteridophytes, New addition, West Bengal.

INTRODUCTION

Pteridophytes are second to the angiosperm in most floras (Chandra *et al.* 2008) of the world which occupy a crucial central position in the evolutionary history of plant kingdom between the lower non-seed bearing and higher seed-bearing plants (Rekha and Krishnan 2017) and are represented by approximately 11916 species (composed of ferns and fern-allies) worldwide (PPG I 2016), distributed in different habitats and niches. The pteridophytes constitute an important component of the forest vegetation in India. The pteridophytic flora of India is fairly well known with regard to distribution and abundance of this particular flora. Most Pteridophytes are observed in the Eastern Himalayas, Kerala, Western Ghats and Eastern Ghats (Bir 1988 & Sathiyaraj *et al.*, 2015). They grow in the moist tropical and temperate forests and their occurrence in different eco-geographically threatened regions from sea level to the highest mountains is of much interest. In India, there are about 1200 species of pteridophytes (Chandra 2000, Dey *et al.* 2019 & 2022; Dixit 1984, Fraser-Jenkins *et al.* 2016, 2018 & 2020).

The district Jalpaiguri (Fig. 1) has latitude of 26°15'47" & 26°59'34" N and longitude 88°23'2" & 89°72'30" E with various altitudinal ranges from 100 ft to 3000 ft above the sea level. Geographically the district is situated in the northern part of West

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Bengal with an average rainfall of 3000 mm per annum. District Jalpaiguri is at the conjunction of the 'Duars' and 'Terai' region of the Eastern Himalayan hotspot and being bordered by Bhutan and Bangladesh in the north & south respectively; Darjeeling hills in the west & northwest; Alipurduar district & Cooch Behar district on the east. The district is considered as rich pteridophytic flora and has distinctiveness on account of their species diversity and peculiar formations. In spite of this, fern and fern-allies of the district have not been studied in detail so far, except a few sporadic works (Sikdar *et al.* 1983; Ghosh *et al.* 2004; Paul 2012).

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Fresh collections have been made from a number of places (covering from all the 9 Blocks) throughout of the said district of the state West Bengal. During the floristic studies on Jalpaiguri district, the authors collected some interesting specimens of pteridophytes belonging to several genera. Collected specimens were purely identified by AKS & VKR and through consultation of relevant literature (Ghosh *et al.* 2004; Kholia 2014; Fraser-Jenkins *et al.* 2015; Fraser-Jenkins & Kandel 2019; Kandel & Fraser-Jenkins 2020; Fraser-Jenkins *et al.* 2016, 2018, & 2020 and Soni *et al.* 2020-2022 etc.) and comparing with digital images of vouchers and type-specimens deposited in various herbaria. The collected specimens have been deposited in the BSI-Herbarium, Arunachal Pradesh Regional Centre (ARUN!) and herbarium (Dept. of Life Science), Govt. Model School, Mal (GMSMH), Jalpaiguri. Careful scrutiny of relevant literatures (Mehra & Bir 1964; Sikdar *et al.* 1983; Ghosh *et al.* 2004; Paul 2012) of Jalpaiguri district as well as plains of West Bengal and hence the occurrence of 26 different Fern and Fern allies has been recorded for the first time in the said district. Most of the pteridophytic taxa has earlier been reported from Darjeeling and Kalimpong hilly region of West Bengal through herbarium study but few of them were not yet reported till date from the plains of West Bengal and Darjeeling-Kalimpong hills as a living specimen. Extensive studies of such pteridophytes with botanical description, distribution, details of specimen studied and notes on ecology etc. have been provided below along with the photographs of examined specimens.

We used GeoCAT (Bachman *et al.* 2011) to help assessing the Extent of Occurrence (EOO) and the Area of Occupancy (AOO) of the discussed taxa in Jalpaiguri, West Bengal (India). In addition, their conservation status in West Bengal (India) based on the International Union for Conservation of Nature and Natural Resources (IUCN) Red List Categories and Criteria (IUCN 2017-1) are evaluated. During the present investigation, generic delimitation of Fraser-Jenkins (2010) is followed.

TAXONOMIC TREATMENT

1. *Huperzia phlegmaria* (L.) Rothm., Feddes Repert. Spec. Nov. Regni Veg. 54:62.1944; Fraser-Jenkins, Kandel & Pariyar, Ferns Fern-Allies Nepal: 1:50. 2015; Fraser-Jenkins, *et al.*, Annot. Checkl. Ind. Pterid., 1:14. 2016. **(Plate I : A)**

Lycopodium phlegmaria L., Sp. Pl. 2: 1101. 1753.

Plants 1-2 ft. long, hanging on trees, epiphytic, dichotomously branched in many ranks; microphylls thick coriaceous, arises in four indistinct rows, deltate to awl shaped, margins entire, apex acute, sharp pointed; sporangia catkin like, terminal, arises at the end of old terminal branches, repeatedly dichotomously branched; sporophylls small, compact, ovate, apiculate at apex, spore trilete.

Specimen Examined: India, West Bengal, Jalpaiguri, Sipchu forest beat, Matiali bazaar, Chalsa, *M. Dey & A. K. Soni* MD015/21, 27° 004' N and 88° 881' E, Alt: 490m ± 150, 28/07/2021, (ARUN!); sub as “Angiospermic species” in error; det. into the all sections of specimen examined by AKS in August of 2021.

Habitat and Ecology: *Huperzia phlegmaria* growing in epiphytic habitat mainly on tree trunks at *ca.* 500-1000 m.

Local Distribution in West Bengal: Darjeeling, Jalpaiguri (present study) and Kalimpong hills.

Distribution in India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam State, Karnataka, Kerala, Meghalaya, Nagaland, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura and West Bengal (Fraser-Jenkins *et al.* 2016)

2. *Equisetum arvense* L. subsp. *diffusum* (D.Don) Fraser-Jenk., Fraser-Jenkins, Kandel & Pariyar, Ferns Fern-Allies Nepal: 1:87. 2015; Fraser-Jenkins, *et al.*, Annot. Checkl. Ind. Pterid., 1:62. 2016. (Plate I: B)

Equisetum diffusum D.Don, Prodr. Flor. Nepal. : 19. 1824.

Plants lithophytic, terrestrial, erect, herbaceous with perennial under ground rhizome; rhizome erect, brown; aerial stems annual, monomorphic, 10-50 cm tall, 0.1-0.3 cm in diam., branched, internodes 1.5-6 cm, main stem axis with 4-8 ridged, each side of ridge raised and forming edges reaching lower sheath of the teeth, with a deep groove going through back of sheath, sheath teeth 5-10, 0.4-0.5×0.1-0.4 cm, lanceolate, leathery, caudate at apex, persistent; strobilus terete, 1-6×0.5 cm, apex blunt; stalk prolonged when mature, 1-1.3 cm.; sporangiophores 0.5 cm apart, peltate, stalked; sporangia 7-8 whorled, dehiscing longitudinally, light brown; spores spherical, chlorophyllous, with several elaters.

Specimen Examined: India, West Bengal, Jalpaiguri, Samsing (Matiali), Odlabari-Sevok, road side, *M. Dey & A. K. Soni* MD277/22, 26° 177' N and 89° 425' E, Alt: 800m ± 150, 20/11/2022, (ARUN !); det. into the all sections of specimen examined by AKS in December of 2022.

Habitat and Ecology: Terrestrial and grows on water logged, marshy humid place; alt. *ca.* 200-1000 m.

Local Distribution in West Bengal: Darjeeling, Jalpaiguri (present study) and Kalimpong hills.

Distribution in India: Arunachal Pradesh, Bihar, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland, Sikkim, Uttarakhand and West Bengal

(Fraser-Jenkins, *et al.* 2016).

3. *Cyathea gigantea* (Wall, ex Hook.) Holttum, Gard. Bull. Straights Settle. 8(4): 318. 1935; Fraser-Jenkins, Kandel & Pariyar, Ferns Fern-Allies Nepal: 1:151. 2015; Fraser-Jenkins, *et al.*, Annot. Checkl. Ind. Pterid., 1:123. 2016. **(Plate I: C)**
Alsophila gigantea Wall ex Hook., Sp. Fil. 1: 53. 1844.

Terrestrial, tree trunk about 10 cm diameter, persistent swollen bases of stipes about a meter, bearing crown of fronds at the apex; trunk densely covered by scales, oblong, 5×1.5 mm and lanceolate, uniformly dark brown, glossy, long acuminate, entire; stipes tufted, 80×8 cm, chestnut brown, glossy, adaxially grooved, densely scaly at the swollen base; lamina bipinnate, deltoid about 150×100 cm, primary pinnae about 12 pairs, spreading, alternate, distinctly stalked, about 20 cm apart, oblong-lanceolate, 45×20 cm, apex acuminate, base truncate; secondary pinnae about 20 pairs, catadromous, spreading, alternate, about 2 cm apart, truncate, margin usually lobed, rarely crenate; costa and costules well distinct below, texture herbaceous, pale brown, soft, acicular hairs densely distributed on the adaxial side of the secondary rachis and costa in addition to few small, narrow, linear, pale brown scales; sori three to five pairs, spherical, forming two zigzag rows, exindusiate, sporangia numerous, compact, paraphyses mingled with sporangia; spores light brown.

Specimen Examined: India, West Bengal, Jalpaiguri, Lataguri Forest, Jurabandha-Belakoba Road (Rajganj), *M. Dey & A. K. Soni* MD020/20, 26° 76'N and 88° 89'E, Alt: 300m ± 150, 26/01/2020, (ARUN!); det. into the all sections of specimen examined by AKS in August of 2021.

Habitat and Ecology: Terrestrial, growing at slopes of semi open forest; alt. *ca.* 400-1200 m.

Local Distribution in West Bengal: Darjeeling, Jalpaiguri (present study) and Kalimpong hills.

Distribution in India: Andaman & Nicobar, Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam State, Chhattisgarh, Jharkhand, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland, Odisha, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura and West Bengal (Fraser-Jenkins *et al.* 2016).

4. *Hypolepis polypodioides* (Blume) Hook., Sp. Fil. 2: 63. 1852; Fraser-Jenkins, Kandel & Pariyar, Ferns Fern-Allies Nepal: 1:163. 2015; Fraser-Jenkins, *et al.*, Annot. Checkl. Ind. Pterid., 1:159. 2016. **(Plate I: D)**

Cheilanthes polypodioides Blume, Enum. PL. Javae 2: 139. 1828.

Plants terrestrial, erect; rhizome creeping, long, hairy; hairs brown, 0.1-0.2 cm; fronds tri-pinnate, 40-90×8-25 cm; stipe distant, stramineous, 20-40 cm; lamina deltate to lanceolate, pubescent, pale jointed hairs, 20-60×8-25 cm; pinnae alternate, basal pair opposite, 10-20 pairs, stalked, oblong-lanceolate, acuminate, 4-13×2-5 cm; pinnules 20 pairs, alternate, sub-sessile, oblong, deeply lobed, apex rounded, 1-4×0.4-1.5 cm; ultimate

segments opposite, 10 pairs, oblong, entire; sori marginal, circular, brown; sporangium ovoid, dark brown; spore bilateral, spinulose, brown.

Specimen Examined: India, West Bengal, Jalpaiguri, Haldibari-Jalpaiguri main road side near Pandapara Kalibari Mandir, *M. Dey & A. K. Soni* MD061/19, 26° 53' N and 88° 70' E, Alt: 150m ± 10, 11/08/2019, (ARUN !); det. into the all sections of specimen examined by AKS in August of 2021.

Habitat and Ecology: Terrestrial and grows on shady humid or open places; alt. *ca.* 150-1000 m.

Local Distribution in West Bengal: Darjeeling, Jalpaiguri (present study) and Kalimpong hills.

Distribution in India: Arunachal Pradesh, Assam State, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Manipur, Meghalaya, Nagaland, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal (Fraser-Jenkins *et al.* 2016).

5. *Lindsaea ensifolia* Sw., in Schrader, J. Bot. 1800, (2): 77. 1801; Fraser-Jenkins, Kandel & Pariyar, Ferns Fern-Allies Nepal: 1:192. 2015; Fraser-Jenkins, *et al.*, Annot. Checkl. Ind. Pterid., 1:182. 2016. **(Plate I: E)**

Adiantum ensifolium (Sw.) Voir., in Lamarck, Encycl. Meth. Bot., Suppl. 1,1(1): 139. 1810.

Plant terrestrial; rhizome short creeping with slender roots; scales basifixed, linear, entire acuminate, dark brown; fronds 40×15 cm, terminal pinnae rhomboid; stipes long up to 20 cm, brown; lamina linear lanceolate; pinnae 5-10 pairs, alternate, terminal pinnae oblique at base, lateral pinnae cuneate base, entire, acuminate; costae slightly grooved, areoles, veins anastomosing; sori marginal, elongated, dark brown, opening towards the outside; spores trilete, brown.

Specimen Examined: India, West Bengal, Jalpaiguri, Near Sipchu SSB Camp Road, *M. Dey & A. K. Soni* MD003/19, 26° 95' N and 88° 88' E, Alt: 395m ± 50, 28/03/2019 & 09/08/2021, (ARUN !); det. into the all sections of specimen examined by AKS in August of 2021.

Habitat and Ecology: Terrestrial, growing in shady humid places of semi-open forest; alt. *ca.* 400-800 m.

Local Distribution in West Bengal: Darjeeling, Jalpaiguri (present study) and Kalimpong hills.

Distribution in India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam State, Chhattisgarh, Goa, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland, Odisha, Rajasthan, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura and West Bengal (Fraser-Jenkins *et al.* 2016).

6. *Adiantum caudatum* L. Mant. Pl. Altera. 308. 1771; Fraser-Jenkins, Kandel & Pariyar, Ferns Fern-Allies Nepal: 1:203. 2015; Fraser-Jenkins, *et al.*, Annot. Checkl. Ind.

Pterid., 1:201. 2016. **(Plate I: F)**

Adiantum lyratum Blanco, Fl. Filipinas 832. 1837.

s Terrestrial, lithophytic; rhizome erect, thick, densely scaly; scales lanceolate, up to 3×0.25 mm, dark brown at the centre, gradually become pale brown towards the margin, opaque, acuminate, entire; stipes numerous, tufted, 15×0.15 cm, dark brown, rounded below, grooved above, densely covered by long, pale brown, hairs; fronds often proliferate; lamina oblong-lanceolate, simply pinnate; pinnae 15-20 pairs, alternate sessile, basal few pairs slightly reduced and deflexed, largest pinna about 1.5×0.5 cm, dimidiate, lower half completely excised, acroscopic base truncate, upper margin lobed half way or more to the lower margin, apex subacute or rounded; veins very slightly distinct above and below, dichotomously branched; texture herbaceous; sori marginal, reniform, indusia densely or sparsely pubescent above, spores trilete, pale brown.

Specimen Examined: India, West Bengal, Jalpaiguri, Jalpaiguri Town Congress Para–Municipality Health Centre, *M. Dey & A. K. Soni* MD046/19, 26° 53' N and 88° 70' E, Alt: 180m ± 80, 16/07/2019, (ARUN!); det. into the all sections of specimen examined by AKS in August of 2021.

Habitat and Ecology: Lithophytic, growing under the shades of semi-open forest in elev. of 200-1000 m.

Local Distribution in West Bengal: Burdwan, Hooghly, Darjeeling Kalimpong hills, Jalpaiguri (present study), Malda and Nadia.

Distribution in India: Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam State, Karnataka, Kerala, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland, Odisha, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura and West Bengal (Fraser-Jenkins *et al.* 2016).

7. *Adiantum incisum* Forssk., Fl. Aegypt. Arab.: 187.1775; subsp. *incisum*, Fraser-Jenkins, *et al.*, Annot. Checkl. Ind. Pterid., 1:204. 2016. **(Plate I: G)**

Adiantum capillus-gorgonis Webb, in Hooker, Niger Fl. 192, 193. 1849.

Plants lithophytic; rhizome erect, scaly; scale brown, lanceolate, acuminate, 0.8-1×0.2-0.3 cm; fronds pinnate, lanceolate, 10-30×2-4.5 cm; stipe chestnut, shining, scaly at base; rachis hairy, ultimate end with rooting buds; pinnae green, lobed at acroscopic side, cuneate, sessile, hairy, 10-20 pairs, alternate; sori 2-4, linear, covered by false indusium, marginal, greyish; sporangium globose, golden-brown; spore trilete tetrahedral, brown.

Specimen Examined: India, West Bengal, Throughout Jalpaiguri district, *M. Dey & A. K. Soni* M104/21, Alt: 400m ± 100, 17/10/2021, (ARUN !); det. into the all sections of specimen examined by AKS in December of 2021.

Habitat and Ecology: Lithophytic, growing in shades of semi-open places; alt. *ca.* 500-1000 m.

Local Distribution in West Bengal: Darjeeling, Jalpaiguri (present study) and Kalimpong hills.

Distribution in India: Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam State, Bihar, Chandigarh, Chhattisgarh, Goa, Gujarat, Jharkhand, Haryana, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Nagaland, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Odisha, Punjab, Rajasthan, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal (Fraser-Jenkins *et al.* 2016).

8. *Aleuritopteris bicolor* (Roxb.) Fraser-Jenk., Fern Gaz. 18(5): 223. 2009; Fraser-Jenkins, Kandel & Pariyar, Ferns Fern-Allies Nepal: 1:232. 2015; Fraser-Jenkins, *et al.*, Annot. Checkl. Ind. Pterid., 1:221. 2016. **(Plate I: H&I)**

Pteris bicolor Roxb., in Griffith, Calcutta J. Nat. Hist. 4: 507-1844 (and as "*Cheilanthes discolor*" Griff, loc. cit. 466, sphalm.).

Plants lithophytic, terrestrial; rhizome short, erect, 0.8 cm in diam., fronds 15-40 × 4-12 cm, deltate-ovate, bi-pinnate; stipe 8-15 cm, brown, scaly; scales bicolorous, linear; lamina as long as the stipe, 7-25 × 4-10 cm, coriaceous, adaxially green, abaxially with white farina; pinnae 4-8 pairs, sub-opposite, basal pinnae largest, deltate, 2-6 × 1-4 cm, upper pinnae lanceolate; pinnules sessile, lanceolate, deeply lobed, basiscopic pinnule of basal pinnae pair largest; sori marginal, indusiate; sporangium brown, globose, spores globose, trilete, pale brown.

Specimen Examined: India, West Bengal, Jalpaiguri, Diana forest, Nagrakata, Chamurchi, *M. Dey & A. K. Soni* MD127/20, 26° 96' N and 88° 94' E, Alt: 200 m ± 100, 27/09/2020, (ARUN !); det. into the all sections of specimen examined by AKS in August of 2021.

Habitat and Ecology: Lithophytic, mainly growing on shady places near the water bodies and canals of Tea Garden in present study; alt. *ca.* 200-1000 m.

Local Distribution in West Bengal: Darjeeling, Alipurduar, Jalpaiguri (present study) and Kalimpong hills.

Distribution in India: Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam State, Bihar, Chandigarh, Chhattisgarh, Goa, Haryana, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Jharkhand, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Odisha, Rajasthan, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal (Fraser-Jenkins, *et al.* 2016).

9. *Ceratopteris thalictroides* (L.) Brongn., Bull. Sci. Soc. Philom. Paris 1821. 183. 1822; subsp. *thalictroides*, Fraser-Jenkins, Kandel & Pariyar, Ferns Fern-Allies Nepal: 1:256. 2015; Fraser-Jenkins, *et al.*, Annot. Checkl. Ind. Pterid., 1:236. 2016. **(Plate I: J)** *Acrostichum thalictroides* L., Sp. Pl. 2: 1070. 1753.

Plants aquatic, stocked, bearing thick fibrous, long roots densely on the abaxial side, apex covered by scales; scales soft, uniformly pale brown, about 2×4 mm, ovate, acute, entire, comprising small, curved cells all over; fronds arranged in rosette; stipes up to 25×1.5 cm, terete, fleshy, pale green, densely ridged all over with few scattered scales;

lamina dimorphous, sterile lamina bi-pinnatifid to tripinnate, glabrous, ovate, about 28×18 cm, acute, cuneate, primary pinnae about five pairs, slightly ascending, alternate, up to 8 cm apart, distinctly stalked, up to 9×6 cm, secondary pinnae about four pairs, alternate, shortly stalked, broadly deltoid or ovate, about 4×4 cm, pinnatifid about 2-3 mm to the costa, ultimate lobes linear, oblong or variously shaped, apex acute, margin entire; veins slightly distinct; fertile lamina ovate, up to 40×20 cm, tripinnate, ultimate segment needle like, up to 5×0.2 cm, acute, margin reflexed and completely covering the lower surface on which two rows of larger sporangia are borne; spores trilete.

Specimen Examined: India, West Bengal, Throughout Jalpaiguri district within aquatic bodies or adjacent to wet land areas, *M. Dey & A. K. Soni* MD69/20, Alt: 100m ± 50, 02/08/2020, (ARUN!); det. into the all sections of specimen examined by AKS in August of 2021.

Habitat and Ecology: Aquatic, grows in aquatic bodies or adjacent to water bodies; at. ca. 150-800 m.

Local Distribution in West Bengal: Throughout West Bengal except hills district

Distribution in India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam State, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Goa, Haryana, Himachal Pradesh, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Nagaland, Odisha, Punjab, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal (Fraser-Jenkins *et al.* 2016).

10. *Coniogramme serrulata* (Blume) Fée, Gen. Fil.: 167, t.14b, f.2 .1850; Fraser-Jenkins, Kandel & Pariyar, Ferns Fern-Allies Nepal: 1:272. 2015; Fraser-Jenkins, *et al.*, Annot. Checkl. Ind. Pterid., 1:241. 2016. (**Plate II: K**)

Gymnogramma serrulata Blume, Enum. PL Javae 2: 113. 1828.

Plants terrestrial, erect; rhizome wide, creeping; fronds 45-85×15-30 cm, simple pinnate, basal pinnae with an accessory basisopic pinnae, deltate, ovate; stipe 20-30 cm, stramineous, scaly at base; pinnae 2- 6 pairs, simple, lanceolate, basal pair pinnate, 10-25×2-4 cm, base truncate, margins serrate, acuminate, texture coriaceous, veins forked, venation free; sori linear, exindusiate; sporangium brown, spherical; sporetrilete, light brown, smooth.

Specimen Examined: India, West Bengal, Jalpaiguri, Bagrakote, Aibheel Tea garden (Matiali), Odlabari, *M. Dey & A. K. Soni* MD177/22, 26° 85' N and 88° 67' E, Alt: 590m ± 80, 13/11/2022, (ARUN!); det. into the all sections of specimen examined by AKS in December of 2022.

Habitat and Ecology: Terrestrial and grows on shady humid places at 600-1200 m. ele.

Local Distribution in West Bengal: Darjeeling, Jalpaiguri (present study) and Kalimpong hills.

Distribution in India: Arunachal Pradesh, Assam State, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Manipur, Meghalaya, Nagaland, Sikkim, Uttarakhand and West Bengal (Fraser-Jenkins *et al.* 2016).

11. *Pteris aspericaulis* Wall. ex J. Agardh, Rec. Spec. Gen. Pter. 22. 1839; Fraser-Jenkins, Kandel & Pariyar, Ferns Fern-Allies Nepal: 1:310. 2015; Fraser-Jenkins, *et al.*, Annot. Checkl. Ind. Pterid., 1:278. 2016. **(Plate II: L)**

Pteris quadriaurita var. *aspericaulis* (Wall, ex J. Agardh) Bedd., Handb. Ferns Brit. India 111. 1883.

Plants lithophytic, terrestrial, erect; rhizome sub-erect, short, scaly; scales lanceolate, entire, brown, acuminate, 0.2-0.5×0.1-0.2 cm; fronds monomorphic, pinnate, sub-coriaceous, 40-100×12-22 cm; stipe rough, pinkish, stramineous in maturity, 10-40 cm; lamina lanceolate, green, 30-70×12-20 cm; pinnae 8-15 pairs, alternate, linear-lanceolate, acuminate, basal pair largest, bipartite, 6-10×3-5 cm; pinnules oblong, opposite, 10-20 pairs, entire, apiculate, 3-5×0.5-1 cm; setae present at the junction of costa and costules; veins distinct, prominent, forked, venation free; sori marginal, linear, indusiate; sporangium globose, brown; spore tetrahedral trilete, brown, tuberculate.

Specimen Examined: India, West Bengal, Jalpaiguri, Domohoni–Maynaguri Road side near RPF training centre, *M. Dey & A. K. Soni* MD233/22, 26° 56' N and 88° 78' E, Alt: 150 m ± 50, 20/10/2022, (ARUN !); sub as "*Pteris biaurita*" in error, det. into the all sections of specimen examined by AKS in December of 2022.

Habitat and Ecology: Terrestrial and grows on shady humid places at 150-1200 m.

Local Distribution in West Bengal: Darjeeling, Jalpaiguri (present study) and Kalimpong hills.

Distribution in India: Arunachal Pradesh, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Manipur, Meghalaya, Sikkim, Uttarakhand and West Bengal (Fraser-Jenkins *et al.* 2016).

12. *Pteris ensiformis* N. L. Burman, Fl. Indica. 230. 1768; Fraser-Jenkins, Kandel & Pariyar, Ferns Fern-Allies Nepal: 1:330. 2015; Fraser-Jenkins, *et al.*, Annot. Checkl. Ind. Pterid., 1:286. 2016. **(Plate II: M)**

Plants terrestrial, erect; rhizome ascending, scaly; scale lanceolate, entire, acuminate, brown, 0.3×0.1 cm; fronds dimorphic, sterile frond pinnate, 10-25×5-10 cm; stipe stramineous, 5-10 cm; pinnae 3 pairs, stalked, alternate, linear, acuminate, 2.5-5×0.4-0.5 cm, basal pinnae bi-partite; pinnule two pairs, opposite, elliptic, serrate, acute, 3×1 cm; fertile fronds pinnate, ca. 10-50×10-20 cm; veins distinct, forked; sori linear, along margin, indusiate, brown; sporangium globose, dark brown; spore tetrahedral, tuberculated, brown.

Specimen Examined: India, West Bengal, Jalpaiguri, Teesta Udyan park, Holy Child school campus, *M. Dey & A. K. Soni* MD198/22, 26° 53' N and 88° 70' E, Alt: 150m ± 50, 16/09/2022, (ARUN !); det. by AKS in December of 2022.

Habitat and Ecology: Terrestrial, and grows on shady humid places at 150-800 m. elev.

Local Distribution in West Bengal: Darjeeling, Jalpaiguri (present study) and Kalimpong hills.

Distribution in India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam State, Kerala, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura and West Bengal (Fraser-Jenkins *et al.* (2016).

13. *Pteris kathmanduensis* Fraser-Jenk. & T.G. Walker, Taxon. Revis. Three Hundred Indian Subcont. Pterid. 415. 2008; Fraser-Jenkins, Kandel & Pariyar, Ferns Fern-Allies Nepal: 1:333. 2015; Fraser-Jenkins, *et al.*, Annot. Checkl. Ind. Pterid., 1:292. 2016. **(Plate II: N)**

Plants terrestrial, erect, long up to 2 ft.; rhizome ascending, scaly; scale lanceolate, entire; fronds large, stipe slightly brownish; lamina long, with up to 10 pairs of pinnae, alternate, linear, acute to acuminate, well-spaced out towards the base of the lowest pinnae, the sinus between segments usually reaching down to a little above the costa or some lower ones to the costa, 2 to 3 lowest developed compound basis copic pinnules on each lowest pinna; veins distinct, forked; sori linear, along margin, indusiate, brown; sporangium globose, brown; spore tetrahedral, tuberculated, brown.

Specimen Examined: India, West Bengal, Jalpaiguri, Domohoni-Basusuba Road, Bara Kamat (Maynaguri), *M. Dey & A. K. Soni* MD335/22, 26° 59'N and 88° 76'E, Alt: 170m ± 35, 02/11/2022, (ARUN !); det. into the all sections of speciemen examined by AKS in December of 2022.

Habitat and Ecology: Terrestrial, grows in shady humid places at 200-1000 m. elev.

Local Distribution in West Bengal: Darjeeling, Jalpaiguri (present study) and Kalimpong hills.

Distribution in India: Arunachal Pradesh, Meghalaya, Sikkim, Uttarakhand and West Bengal (Fraser-Jenkins *et al.* 2016).

14. *Pteris multifida* Poir. In Lam. Ency. Method. Bot. 5: 714. 1804; Fraser-Jenkins, Kandel & Pariyar, Ferns Fern-Allies Nepal: 1:337. 2015; Fraser-Jenkins, *et al.*, Annot. Checkl. Ind. Pterid., 1:295. 2016. **(Plate II: O)**

Pycnodoria multifida (Poir.) Small, Ferns S. E. States 104, 468. 1938.

Plants terrestrial, lithophytic; rhizome erect, short, scaly; roots thin; scaly basifixed, lanceolate, dark brown; fronds 18-35×10-12 cm, sterile 20 cm, fertile 30-35 cm long; stipes 10-20 cm, dark brown, glabrous; lamina 10-15 cm long; pinnae 2 pairs with the lower large ones, bipartite, linear; fertile margin entire and sterile crenate, obtuse; pinnules 3-5 cm long, linear oblong, glabrous, main vein distinct; sori marginal, elongated, indusiate, paraphyses present; spores trilete dark brown, tuberculate.

Specimen Examined: India, West Bengal, Jalpaiguri, PWD more near Karala river bank (Jalpaiguri town), *M. Dey & A. K. Soni* MD239/22, 26° 52'15' N and 88° 71'96' E, Alt: 80m ± 50, 11/07/2022, (ARUN !); det. into the all sections of speciemen examined by AKS in December of 2022.

Habitat and Ecology: Lithophytic, terrestrial grows on shady humid places and wall

PLATE-I : **A.** *Huperziaphlegmaria* (L.) Rothm.; **B.** *Equisetum arvense* L. subsp. *diffusum* Fraser-Jenk.; **C.** *Cyathea gigantea* (Wall. Ex Hook.) Holttum; **D.** *Hypolepis polypodioides* (Blume) Hook.; **E.** *Lindsaea ensifolia* Sw.; **F.** *Adiantum caudatum* L.; **G.** *Adiantum incisum* subsp. *incisum* Forssk.; **H.** & **I.** *Aleuritopteris bicolor* (Roxb.) Fraser-Jenk.

PLATE-II : J. *Ceratopteris thalictroides* (L.) Brongn. subsp. *thalictroides*; K. *Coniogramme serrulata* (Blume) Fée; L. *Pteris aspericaulis* Wall. ex J. Agardh.; M. *Pteris ensiformis* N. L. Burman.; N. *Pteris kathmanduensis* Fraser-Jenk. & T.G. Walker; O. *Pteris multifida* Poir.; P. *Pteris scabririgens* Fraser-Jenkins, Verm & T.G. Walker; Q. *Antrophyum reticulatum* (G. Forst.) Kaulf.; R. & S. *Vittaria elongata* Swartz.

PLATE-III : T. *Thelypteris procera* (Don) Fraser-Jenk.; U. *Dryopteris cochleata* (D. Don) C. Chr.; V. *Polystichum manmeiense* (Christ) Nakaike; W. *Polystichum nepalense* (Spreng.) C. Chr.; X. *Tectaria polymorpha* (Wall, ex Hook.) Copel.; Y. *Nephrolepis radicans* (Burm. f.) Kuhn.; Z. *Leptochilus decurrens* Blume subsp. *hemionitideus*; A1. *Microsorum cuspidatum* (D. Don) Tagawa.

Fig. 2 : Showing the study area (Jalpaiguri Dist.)

Fig. 1 : Map of West Bengal

of ancient buildings; alt. *ca.* 80-700 m.

Local Distribution in West Bengal: Burdwan, Hooghly, Howrah, Kolkata and Paschim Medinipur.

Distribution in India: Uttarakhand and West Bengal (Fraser-Jenkins, *et al.* 2016).

15. *Pteris scabririgens* Fraser-Jenk., S.C. Verma & T.G. Walker, Fraser-Jenkins, Taxon. Revis. Three Hundred Indian Subcont. Pterid. 111. 2008; Fraser-Jenkins, Kandel & Pariyar, Ferns Fern-Allies Nepal: 1:347. 2015; Fraser-Jenkins, *et al.*, Annot. Checkl. Ind. Pterid., 1:300. 2016. **(Plate II: P)**

Plants terrestrial approx. 1 m tall; rhizome short, ascending, apex densely scaly; scales dark brown; fronds clustered; stipe darker at base, 40 cm, distinctly rough, glabrous, adaxially grooved, rachis brown in colour; lamina 2-pinnatifid, ovate, *ca.* 20-50×12-25 cm, bright pink when young, turning green when mature and stiffly papery when dried, glabrous; lateral pinnae 5-11 pairs, opposite, obliquely ascending, basal pairs 5-8 cm apart, basal pair shortly stalked, upper sessile, lanceolate, 12-22×2-4 cm, base obliquely cuneate, pectinately divided to near costae, apex linear-caudate, basal pair of pinnae each with basiscopic pinnule at base; segments 20-30 pairs, subopposite to alternate, oblique in fashion, falcate, progressively smaller distally, base slightly expanded, margins entire, apex mucronate; terminal pinna larger in size, stalked; costae abaxially prominent, light brown, sometimes reddish adaxially, glabrous- adaxially grooved with short toothed alongside groove near junction with costules; veins conspicuous on both surfaces, oblique, 2-forked from base; sori marginal spreads 2/3rd of the margin left the apex portion, linear, indusiate; sporangium globose, brown; spore tetrahedral, brown.

Specimen Examined: India, West Bengal, Jalpaiguri, Khumani-Sipchu road, Meenglas Tea garden adjacent (Matiali), *M. Dey & A. K. Soni* MD377/22, 27° 00' N and 88° 82' E, Alt: 600m ± 150, 02/12/2022, (ARUN !); det. into the all sections of specimen examined by AKS in December of 2022.

Habitat and Ecology: Terrestrial, grows in marshy and shady slopes of open of forest at 600-1200 m. elev.

Local Distribution in West Bengal: Darjeeling, Jalpaiguri (present study) and Kalimpong hills.

Distribution in India: Arunachal Pradesh, Meghalaya, Nagaland, Sikkim and West Bengal (Fraser-Jenkins *et al.* 2016).

16. *Antrophyum reticulatum* (G.Forst.) Kaulf., Enum. Fil. 198. 1824; Fraser-Jenkins, Kandel & Pariyar, Ferns Fern-Allies Nepal: 1:374. 2015; Fraser-Jenkins, *et al.*, Annot. Checkl. Ind. Pterid., 1:323. 2016. **(Plate II: Q)**

Hemionitis reticulata G. Forst., Fl. Ins. Austr. 79. 1786.

Plants epiphytic, lithophyte, 20-35×3-5 cm; rhizome creeping, densely scaly; scales 2×0.1 cm, apex acuminate, base broad, margin toothed, blackish-brown; Stripe absent or

very small; lamina simple, 12-38×2-3 cm, apex acuminate, broadest above the middle; midrib absent; veins distinct above and below, copiously anastomosing, areoles very long, narrow and distinctly raise on the upper surface, without any included veinlets; texture coriaceous; sori born along the reticulate veins, linear, immersed; spores oval, tetrahedral, brown.

Specimen Examined: India, West Bengal, Jalpaiguri, road side area Lataguri forest, common in Mal, Nagrakata, Kranti & Matiali block, *M. Dey & A. K. Soni* MD082/21, 26° 72' N and 88° 79' E, Alt: 450m ± 150, 26/09/2021, (ARUN !); det. into the all sections of speciemen examined by AKS in December of 2021.

Habitat and Ecology: Epiphytic, growing on main tree trunks at elev. of 400-1200 m.

Local Distribution in West Bengal: Darjeeling, Jalpaiguri (present study) and Kalimpong hills.

Distribution in India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam State, Kerala, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu and West Bengal (Fraser-Jenkins *et al.* 2016).

17. *Vittaria elongata* Swartz, Syn. Fil. 109, 302.1806; Fraser-Jenkins, Kandel & Pariyar, Ferns Fern-Allies Nepal: 1:378. 2015; Fraser-Jenkins, *et al.*, Annot. Checkl. Ind. Pterid., 1:326. 2016. **(Plate II: R&S)**

Oetosis elongata (Sw.) Greene, Pittonia 4: 106. 1900.

Plants epiphytic, pendulous; rhizome creeping, scaly; scales blackish-brown, lanceolate, margin toothed, acuminate, 0.6-0.8×0.1-0.2cm; lamina simple, tufted, 50-90×0.3-0.5 cm, linear, entire, attenuated, green; stipe 1-7 cm, glabrous; sori marginal, linear, elongated, within shallow grooves; sporangium globose, brown; spore monolete, bilateral, reniform, pale-green.

Specimen Examined: India, West Bengal, Throughout Jalpaiguri district, *M. Dey & A. K. Soni* MD83/20, Alt: 300m ± 150, 02/08/2020, (ARUN!); det. into the all sections of speciemen examined by AKS in November of 2021.

Habitat and Ecology: Epiphytic on main tree trunks at alt. of 300-1000 m.

Local Distribution in West Bengal: Alipurduar, Coochbehar, Darjeeling Kalimponghills, Malda and Uttar & Dakshin Dinajpur.

Distribution in India: Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam State, Karnataka, Kerala, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, and West Bengal (Fraser-Jenkins *et al.* 2016).

18. *Thelypteris procera* (D.Don) Fraser-Jenk., Taxon. Revis. Three Hundred Indian Subcont. Pterid. 183. 2008; Fraser-Jenkins, *et al.*, Annot. Checkl. Ind. Pterid., 1:479. 2016; Fraser-Jenkins, Kandel & Pariyar, Ferns Fern-Allies Nepal: 2:79. 2019. **(Plate II: T)**

Nephrodium procerum D.Don, Prodr. Fl. Nepal. 6. 1824.

Plants terrestrial, erect; rhizome creeping, scaly; scales lanceolate, brown, 0.5-1×0.3-0.4 cm; frond pinnate, distant, 60-80×12-20 cm; stipe 15-30 cm, stramineous; lamina lanceolate, pubescent, green, herbaceous, 45-60×12-20 cm; pinnae alternate, 20-25 pairs, lanceolate, acuminate, middle pair largest, 12-20×2-3 cm, basal pair gradually decreasing, 8-10×1-1.5 cm; pinnules deeply lobed, opposite, 10-15 pairs, oblong, entire, acute, pubescent; veins distinct, simple; sori round, submarginal, indusiate, hairy; sporangium globose, golden brown; spore monolet, reniform, pale, perispore folded.

Specimen Examined: India, West Bengal, Jalpaiguri, Lataguri forest near Mahakal Mandir, *M. Dey & A. K. Soni* MD123/21, 26° 70' N and 88° 77' E, Alt: 130m ± 45, 24/10/2021, (ARUN !); det. into the all sections of specimen examined by AKS in December of 2021.

Habitat and Ecology: Terrestrial and grows on shady humid places at 100-800 m.

Local Distribution in West Bengal: Coochbehar, Darjeeling and Kalimpong hills.

Distribution in India: Arunachal Pradesh, Assam State, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland, Sikkim, Tripura, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal (Fraser-Jenkins *et al.* 2016).

19. *Dryopteris cochleata* (D.Don) C.Chr., Index Fil. 258. 1905; Fraser-Jenkins, *et al.*, Annot. Checkl. Ind. Pterid., 2:235 2018; Fraser-Jenkins, Kandel & Pariyar, Ferns Fern-Allies Nepal: 2:227. 2019. (**Plate III: U**)

Nephrodium cochleatum D.Don, Prodr. Fl. Nepal. 6. 1824.

Plants lithophytic, terrestrial, erect; rhizome ascending, densely scaly; scales lanceolate, entire, acuminate, light-brown, 0.8-1.5×0.1-0.2 cm; stipe stramineous; fronds bipinnate, dimorphic, fertile fronds narrower, coriaceous, ca. 40-80×10-15 cm; sterile fronds 10-20 cm; lamina lanceolate, 20-35×10-16 cm; pinnae alternate, 10-12 pairs, stalked, lanceolate, acuminate, 5-9×2-3 cm; pinnules oblong, margin serrate, obtuse, basiscopic pinnule longer, 1-3×0.2-0.5 cm, fertile pinnules, oblong, entire, narrow, contracted, 1×0.5 cm; veins distinct, forked; sori globose, indusiate, dark-brown, in two rows, on either side of costules; sporangium globose, dark brown; spore monolet, reniform, perisporate, pale-brown.

Specimen Examined: India, West Bengal, Jalpaiguri, Nagrakata & Sipchu forest beat, *M. Dey & A. K. Soni* MD109/21, 26° 89' N and 88° 84' E, Alt: 310m ± 50, 24/10/2021, (ARUN !); det. into the all sections of specimen examined by AKS in December of 2021.

Habitat and Ecology: *D. cochleata* growing in shady semi humid slopes in open forest of this district at 400-1000 m. elev.

Local Distribution in West Bengal: Darjeeling, Jalpaiguri (present study) and Kalimpong hills.

Distribution in India: Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam State, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Jarkhand, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal (Fraser-Jenkins *et al.* 2018).

20. *Polystichum manmeiense* (Christ) Nakaike, Misc. Publ. Nat. Sci. Mus. Tokyo. 141.1982; Fraser-Jenkins, *et al.*, Annot. Checkl. Ind. Pterid., 2:327. 2018; Fraser-Jenkins, Kandel & Pariyar, Ferns Fern-Allies Nepal: 2:295. 2019. **(Plate III: V)**

Aspidium manmeiense Christ, Bull. Herb. Boissier 6(12): 965. 1898.

Plants lithophytic, terrestrial, erect; rhizome ascending, scaly; scales linear lanceolate, entire, acuminate, brown, ca. 0.4-0.5×0.1-0.2 cm; fronds bipinnate, 15-50×4-6 cm; stipe stramineous, 4-20 cm, scaly; lamina oblong lanceolate, acuminate, abaxially with micro scales, 10-30×4-8 cm; rachis with bulbils; pinnae alternate, 10-15 pairs, stalked, lanceolate, deeply lobed, acute, 2-4×1.2-2.2 cm, abaxially scaly; lobes 4-6 pairs, alternate, basal acroscopic lobes largest; veins distinct, forked; sori round, on either side of costa, indusiate, brown; sporangium globose, dark brown; spore monolet, spherical, minutely spinose, brown.

Specimen Examined: India, West Bengal, Jalpaiguri, Jhalong road side (Nagrakata), M. Dey & A. K. Soni MD195/22, 26° 92' N and 88° 70' E, Alt: 400m ± 100, 18/07/2022, (ARUN !); det. into the all sections of specimen examined by AKS in November of 2022.

Habitat and Ecology: Terrestrial and grows on shady humid places at 500-1200 m.

Local Distribution in West Bengal: Darjeeling, Jalpaiguri (present study) and Kalimpong hills.

Distribution in India: Arunachal Pradesh, Himachal Pradesh, Sikkim, Uttarakhand and West Bengal (Fraser-Jenkins *et al.* 2018).

21. *Polystichum nepalense* (Spreng.) C. Chr., Index Fil. 585. 1906; Fraser-Jenkins, *et al.*, Annot. Checkl. Ind. Pterid., 2:331. 2018; Fraser-Jenkins, Kandel & Pariyar, Ferns Fern-Allies Nepal: 2:300. 2019. **(Plate III: W)**

Polystichum auriculatum D.Don, Prodr. Fl. Nepal. 3. 1824, non (L.) Sw. 1802, nee Schkuhr 1806.

Plants lithophytic, terrestrial, erect; rhizome ascending, sub-erect, scaly; scales linear-lanceolate, entire, acuminate, brown, 0.8-1×0.1-0.2 cm; frond uni-pinnate, 30-60×3-5 cm; stipe stramineous, 10-15 cm, scaly; pinnae contracted at base, lanceolate, acuminate, abaxially with micro scales, 20-45×3-6 cm; rachis without proliferating bulbils; pinnae alternate, ascending, 20-25 pairs, sub-sessile, lanceolate, auricled at acroscopic side, base oblique, margin entire, apex acute, 1.5-3×1-1.5 cm; veins distinct, forked; sori orbicular, in two rows, on pinnae, indusiate, brown; sporangium ovoid, dark brown; spore monolet, spherical, tuberculate, dark brown.

Specimen Examined: India, West Bengal, Jalpaiguri, Meenglass Tea garden

(Matiali), *M. Dey & A. K. Soni* MD200/22, 26° 91' N and 88° 69' E, Alt: 480m ± 30, 18/07/2022, (ARUN !); det. into the all sections of specimen examined by AKS in December of 2022.

Habitat and Ecology: Terrestrial and grows on shady humid places ca. 500-1000 m.

Local Distribution in West Bengal: Darjeeling, Jalpaiguri (present study) and Kalimpong hills.

Distribution in India: Arunachal Pradesh, Himachal Pradesh, Sikkim, Uttarakhand and West Bengal (Fraser-Jenkins *et al.* 2018).

22. *Tectaria polymorpha* (Wall, ex Hook.) Copel., Philipp. J. Sci. 2(6): 413. 1907; Fraser-Jenkins, *et al.*, Annot. Checkl. Ind. Pterid., 2:379. 2018; Fraser-Jenkins, Kandel & Pariyar, Ferns Fern-Allies Nepal: 2:327. 2019. **(Plate III: X)**

Aspidium polymorphum Wall, ex Hook., Sp. Fil. 4: 54-55. 1862.

Plants lithophytic, terrestrial, erect; rhizome sub-erect, scaly; scales linear lanceolate, margin lacerated, acuminate, brown, 0.6-1×0.1-0.2 cm; fronds deltate, uni-pinnate, 30-80×10-25 cm; stipe stramineous, 10-20 cm, scaly; lamina coriaceous, 20-55×10-25 cm; pinnae opposite, 3-8 pairs, sessile, oblong, base round, margin entire, apex acuminate, 10-25×5-6 cm, basal pinnae forked, bipartite; veins distinct, reticulate; sori scattered, globose, indusiate, brown; sporangium globose, dark-brown; spore monoletate, spherical, light brown.

Specimen Examined: India, West Bengal, Jalpaiguri, Khunia more (Nagrakata), *M. Dey & A. K. Soni* MD125/21, 26° 89'N and 88° 91'E, Alt: 470m ± 50, 24/10/2021, (ARUN !); det. into the all sections of specimen examined by AKS in December of 2022.

Habitat and Ecology: Lithophytic, grows on shady humid places and nearby the water bodies; alt. ca. 500-1200 m.

Local Distribution in West Bengal: Darjeeling, Jalpaiguri (present study) and Kalimpong hills.

Distribution in India: Arunachal Pradesh, Assam State, Chhattisgarh, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland, Odisha, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand and West Bengal (Fraser-Jenkins *et al.* 2018).

23. *Nephrolepis radicans* (Burm.f.) Kuhn, Annales Mus. Lugd.-Bat. 4: 285. 1869; Fraser-Jenkins, Kandel & Pariyar, Ferns Fern-Allies Nepal, 3:13. 2020; Fraser-Jenkins, *et al.*, Annot. Checkl. Ind. Pterid., 3:50. 2020. **(Plate III: Y)**

Polypodium radicans Burm.f, Fl. Ind. 233, t. 66, f. 3. 1768.

Plants terrestrial forming tufts of 3-5 fronds, erect, climbing stem runners, producing frond-bearing stocks at irregular intervals; rhizome short, suberect, runners tendril-like, slender at base, proliferous, 1 mm thick, scales on runners sparse, appressed; stipe stramineous, up to 8-10 cm long, sparsely scaly; lamina linear, ca. 50-70×5-7 cm, narrowing towards both ends, pinnate; middle pinnae larger, slightly falcate, moderately acute at apex, auricled at acroscopic

base, fertile pinnae slightly serrate, ca. 4–5×0.6 cm; lower pinnae small and distant, hairs on lamina absent; hairs on costa constantly present; sori submarginal, 20-23 pairs on fully fertile pinnae, round; indusia reniform, with open sinus; spores monolete, brown.

Specimen Examined: India, West Bengal, Jalpaiguri, Khumani-Sipchu road, (Matiali Block), *M. Dey & A. K. Soni* MD401/20, 27° 00' N and 88° 82' E, Alt: 600m ± 15, 12/10/2020, (ARUN !); det. into the all sections of specimen examined by AKS in November of 2021.

Habitat and Ecology: Terrestrial and grows at low elevations from 600 to 900 m often in swampy and adjacent to water logged areas.

Local Distribution in West Bengal: Darjeeling, Jalpaiguri (present study) and Kalimpong hills.

Distribution in India: Assam State, Manipur and West Bengal (Fraser-Jenkins *et al.* 2020).

24. *Leptochilus decurrens* Blume, Enum. Pl. Javae 2: 206. 1828; subsp. *hemionitideus*, Fraser-Jenkins, Kandel & Pariyar, Ferns Fern-Allies Nepal, 3:69. 2020; Fraser-Jenkins, *et al.*, Annot. Checkl. Ind. Pterid., 3:155. 2020. **(Plate III: Z)**

Gymnopteris wallichiana C. Presl, Tent. Pterid. 244. 1836, nom. nud.

Plants lithophytic, terrestrial, marshy habitat, erect; rhizome long, creeping, scaly; scales lanceolate, entire, acuminate, 0.4×0.1 cm; fronds dimorphic, simple, sterile lamina 10-70×4-8 cm; stipe 2-4 cm, winged, lanceolate, glabrous, papery, base cuneate, margin entire, apex acuminate, fertile lamina ca. 10-20×0.3 cm, not distinctly winged, glabrous, grey-brown, covered entirely with sori at the lower surface; veins distinct, reticulate forming areoles; sori elongate to round, between lateral veins, brown; spore oval-reniform, pale-light brown.

Specimen Examined: India, West Bengal, Jalpaiguri, Bagrakote, Washabari Tea garden, Matiali, *M. Dey & A. K. Soni* MD085/21, 26° 88' N and 88° 57' E, Alt: 600m ± 150, 03/10/2021, (ARUN !); det. into the all sections of specimen examined by AKS in August of 2021.

Habitat and Ecology: Lithophytes and the soil bed adjunct to waterfalls; alt. ca. 500-1200 m.

Local Distribution in West Bengal: Darjeeling, Jalpaiguri (present study) and Kalimpong hills.

Distribution in India: Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam State, Karnataka, Kerala, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland, Odisha, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura and West Bengal (Fraser-Jenkins *et al.* 2020).

25. *Loxogramme porcata* Price, Amer. Fern J. 80(1): 4-8. 1990; Fraser-Jenkins, Kandel & Pariyar, Ferns Fern-Allies Nepal, 3:79. 2020; Fraser-Jenkins, *et al.*, Annot. Checkl. Ind. Pterid., 3:187. 2020.

Loxogramme manipurensis S.Das & R.D. Dixit, *Bull. Bot. Surv. India* 38: 84-85, t. 13. 1996.

Plant epiphytic, thick coriaceous, green; rhizome erect, short, scaly, scales ovate, brown, 0.5–0.8×0.1-0.3 cm, acuminate; fronds in apical tuft, monomorphic; stipe indistinct, short; lamina simple, lanceolate, glabrous, attenuated at base, abaxially pale, adaxially deep green, 30-50×3-5 cm, apex caudate-acuminate, mid-vein raised adaxially, usually flat abaxially, straw-coloured or pale green, veins hidden; sori linear, 3-4.5×0.1-0.3 cm, oblique, well-spaced, between mid-vein to frond margin, superficial, ex-indusiate; sporangium globose, brown, spore reniform to lunar, light green, minutely spinous.

Specimen Examined: India, West Bengal, Jalpaiguri, Chapramari Reserve forest, *M. Dey & A. K. Soni* MD202/22, 26° 89' N and 88° 91' E, Alt: 500m ± 50, 18/07/2022, (ARUN !); det. into the all sections of specimen examined by AKS in December of 2022.

Habitat and Ecology: *L. porcata* growing mainly as epiphytes, but somewhat for lithophyte condition in rare case; alt. *ca.* 500-1500 m.

Local Distribution in West Bengal: Darjeeling, Jalpaiguri (present study) and Kalimpong hills.

Distribution in India: Arunachal Pradesh, Himachal Pradesh, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland, Sikkim, Uttarakhand and West Bengal (Fraser-Jenkins *et al.* 2020).

26. *Microsorum cuspidatum* (D.Don) Tagawa, in Hara, Fl. E. Himalaya Report [1] 495. 1966. subsp. *cuspidatum*, Fraser-Jenkins, Kandel & Pariyar, Ferns Fern-Allies Nepal, 3:81. 2020; Fraser-Jenkins, *et al.*, Annot. Checkl. Ind. Pterid., 3:193. 2020. **(Plate III: A1)**

Polypodium lucidum Roxb., in Griffith, Calcutta J. Nat. Hist. 4: 486. 1844, non Rich. 1792.

Plants lithophytic, herb; rhizome thick, creeping, glabrous or with very few broad adpressed scales; stipe articulated on rhizome, 20-50 cm, glabrous; frond 40-100×20-25 cm, imparipinnate, coriaceous, shining green; pinnae 8-25 pairs, linear-lanceolate, stalked, 10-20×2-3.5 cm, entire, apex acuminate; veins indistinct, anastomosing; sori large, globose, in one row on either side of costa, exindusiate, sporangium globose, golden-brown; spore reniform, golden brown.

Specimen Examined: India, West Bengal, Jalpaiguri, Samsing (Matiali), *M. Dey & A. K. Soni* MD079/21, 26° 99' N and 88° 80' E, Alt: 540m ± 10, 26/09/2021, (ARUN !); sub as “*Phymatosorus cuspidatus*” (synonyms) in short slip of memory, det. into the all sections of specimen examined by AKS in August of 2021.

Habitat and Ecology: Mesophyte or lithophyte on shady humid slopes in semi open forest at 400-1000 m elev.

Local Distribution in West Bengal: Darjeeling, Jalpaiguri (present study) and Kalimpong hills.

Distribution in India: Arunachal Pradesh, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland, Sikkim, West Bengal (Fraser-Jenkins *et al.* 2020).

CONSERVATION STATUS

Above depicted all species are collected only highlands of West Bengal (mainly from Darjeeling). At present, all newly reported taxa were collected from different gatherings in Jalpaiguri, West Bengal (India) at up-to 80–950 m. alt. About 5–10 individuals per square kilometre were collected at there for each taxon. The Area of Occupancy (AOO) is 50–100 Km². However, other similar areas of these regions are yet to be explored wholly and it presumes that the depicted species might be spread in similar ecological conditions. Thus, more floristic surveys are required to determine and document the full range of distribution of given taxon. Hence, at present according to IUCN (2017-1) criteria, currently these species is considered as data deficiency (DD) for foot hills region of West Bengal (India).

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